

E-government mechanisms to enhance the participation of citizens and society: Exploratory analysis through the dimension of municipalities

Francisca Tejedo-Romero^{a,*}, Joaquim Filipe Ferraz Esteves Araujo^{b,1}, Ángel Tejada^a, Yolanda Ramírez^a

^a Department of Business Administration, University of Castilla-La Mancha, Plaza de la Universidad, 1, 02071, Albacete, Spain

^b University of Minho, Research Center in Political Science (CICP), Campus de Gualtar, 4710-057, BRAGA, Portugal

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ABSTRACT

The use of information technologies has been a window of opportunity for local governments to increase initiatives and instruments for citizen participation and interaction with society. The electronic interaction of municipalities with citizens may be different depending on the municipality. The objective of this study is to explore how the dimension of Portuguese municipalities can explain the implementation of participatory processes and channels through e-government initiatives to improve participation and interaction with society. Based on the analysis of the municipal information and interaction indexes, our results show that municipalities are increasingly committed to developing online initiatives for citizen participation in a significant way over the years, with the largest municipalities being the ones that implement the most mechanisms. The influence of population size occurs both for information dissemination and for the implementation of citizen participation mechanisms. This result is consistent with stakeholder theory and political cost theory.

This paper contributes to the literature by offering a characterization of the municipalities and the mechanisms carried out to implement citizen participation and interaction initiatives according to the size of the municipality. It claims that policy makers need to pay attention to the capabilities of e-governments tools to better facilitate the e-participation process and provide the necessary channels to get citizens' feedback.

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1. Introduction

Governments are increasingly relying on information and communication technologies (ICTs) to engage with citizens [1,2]. The Internet and ICTs have opened an opportunity for local governments to increase initiatives and tools for citizen participation and their interaction with

society [3]. They provide powerful instruments for diffusion of public information and for the use of interactive communication with citizens in order to share values and opinions among the actors involved in the participatory process with municipalities. Both contribute to improving municipal transparency and revitalizing local democracy by opening a new space for political communication and participation. In essence, the interaction between local governments and society is improved.

The need to bring local entities closer to citizens, as a way of promoting relationships of trust that encourage participation, has been a constant in local political life. Citizen participation refers to any voluntary action by citizens aimed at influencing public decision-making and the management of collective affairs [4]. In this sense, citizen involvement through e-government could be understood as participation in those public affairs that affect society through measures that include online communication, consultation or deliberation to improve interaction with citizens and society.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: Francisca.Tejedo@uclm.es (F. Tejedo-Romero).

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The local political-administrative agenda aims, through the mechanisms available through electronic government, to promote transparency and participation as fundamental values for interaction between municipalities and citizens. Thus, the municipalities have promoted citizen participation with initiatives through their websites, using them as a repository of information and as interactive channels.

The electronic interaction of municipalities with citizens can be different depending on the municipality. Some studies refer, among other explanations, to the importance of the size of the municipality (population size) to justify the existing differences between municipalities. There are municipalities that show less development in the use of online initiatives, offering only information through their website. Other municipalities implement more advanced online initiatives for citizen participation and interaction with society, such as e-mail communication, complaints offices, discussion processes using electronic devices such as forums, chats, blogs, wikis, social networks.

Several studies have analyzed the influence of ICT in improving relations and dialogue between citizens and their public representatives [5–8]. However, the implementation of e-government initiatives that promote interaction between Portuguese municipalities and society is not well studied [9,10,97]. Thus, it is worth analyzing whether online initiatives to improve citizen participation and interaction between Portuguese municipalities and society are improving municipal transparency. Moreover, it is important to know whether this improvement depends on the size of the municipalities. The option of a single-country study may raise legitimate questions about generalization. However, an important advantage of such studies is that they are based on the same set of laws and rules governing the constituent municipalities. This facilitates the development of a better-specified framework with more defensible measures. In addition, the larger number of Portuguese municipalities and their diversity in terms of size make it possible to analyze the effects of population differences. Numerous studies have corroborated size as the most influential variable for the development of municipal transparency initiatives [11–14].

The aim of this paper is to explore how the dimension of the municipalities can explain the implementation of participatory processes and communications channels through the website; as well as the evolution that they have experienced over time. Specifically, institutional electronic initiatives and citizen participation mechanisms to interaction with society are analyzed. Therefore, the study aims to answer the following questions:

Are municipalities committed and involved in promoting online interaction initiatives? Are these mechanisms improving over time? What is the influence of the size of municipalities on the development of online citizen interaction initiatives?

This paper contributes to the literature by offering a characterization of the municipalities and the mechanisms carried out to implement citizen participation and interaction initiatives. The study makes an exploratory analysis to explain the development of these initiatives by considering: (i) the institutional context in which these experiences are framed, (ii) the processes and mechanisms of online citizen participation (iii) the development over the years, and (iv) the influence of the dimension of the municipalities.

2. Literature review and hypothesis development

2.1. Implementation of participation and communication systems in local administrations: municipal e-government

According to the new trends in public management, local governments are implementing a new management philosophy, acquiring a governance model that strengthens institutional autonomy, but also with greater transparency towards society. This allows improving the channels of participation of society in management and, in turn, the implementation of greater control over the results achieved by the municipal government [2,15]. This is justified by the availability of

more information on different aspects related to municipal management [3,16].

In order to adapt to the new management strategies of municipalities, one of the major factors to be considered is transparency. Local governments need to show that they work in harmony with the population, showing a transparent management. In this context, any citizen can consult any information about the political or economic organization through data transfer. A transparent and intelligent government facilitates proximity to the population. This allows to obtain accurate information on those aspects that the citizen demands and on the functioning of the municipality.

This trend to improve the interaction between the municipality and citizens leads to the establishment of direct communication channels between them. These channels improve the information made available to citizens and facilitate their participation in governance using ICT [1, 3]. Thus, e-government is directly related to the potential of ICT to improve government activity and the relationship between public administrations and citizens [3,17]). We are not only situated on a plane linked to management, but rather as an area that reflects dynamics of power, conflict and cooperation in the governmental sphere [18–20].

In this process to increase municipal transparency, e-government is a fundamental tool for participation and communication, since its functionality and content are responsible for transmitting the essence of the municipality's management to citizens and convincing them to trust in its services. Within this context, the different online interaction tools have become, over time, projection tools for any municipality. The promotion of online interaction initiatives between municipalities and citizens and other stakeholders dominates their corporate communication, especially after 2010, where content marketing is used as the main vehicle to force conversation, stimulate demand, and trust in the services provided by municipalities to citizens. These interaction initiatives are facilitating improved communication between organizations and their stakeholders [21,22]. These are Internet applications based on Web 2.0 technology that allow organizations to share information at a high rate, thus fostering interactivity in communication flows [22]. These initiatives to promote online interaction aim to overcome one-way communication, becoming vehicles for greater engagement (data-rich) authentic content and interaction with stakeholders that can reveal more about the communication of Portuguese municipalities with their wider stakeholder communities.

Studies on relationship management [23] reveal that, in the digital era, e-government is necessary to improve relations with strategic stakeholders. In this scenario, these electronic communication tools contribute to the effectiveness of a municipality's communication because they make information more visible and accessible to stakeholders and increase corporate dialogue in the context of voluntary information disclosure [1,3]. Furthermore, local governments can take advantage of the increase of this new participative culture that is developing in many citizens in order to draw their attention toward municipal management, engage them in local public decision-making, and improve government-to-citizen relationships [24].

Although it is possible to find diverse conceptualizations of e-government, the specialized literature tends to highlight four common elements for its definition. The elements are: (a) the use of ICT; (b) the presence of government actions, such as the provision of information, goods and/or public services; (c) the improvement of the relationship between government and citizens; and (d) the existence of strategies to create value to participants [2,25,26].

In this context, along with the consolidation of the Internet and the sustained increase in its penetration rates, government websites were established as channels that provide information, technological applications and a variety of resources made available to citizens [27–29]. These government websites can be assessed based on various models. Fath-Allah et al. [30] (see also [28] evaluate 25 recent models proposed by specialized literature and identify four phases of digital maturity. The phases are: (a) presence, where government agencies merely present

information on the Internet; (b) interaction, a stage in which citizens have the possibility to interact with the public administration; (c) transaction, a stage in which citizens can complete transactions and exchanges through the portals; and (d) integration, where different government agencies share information, which includes social networking applications and e-participation mechanisms.

The evolutionary approach is in a similar line of research. It recognizes that e-government portals evolve and acquire new functionalities as technology advances. This approach identifies five components: (a) information, (b) interaction, (c) transaction, (d) integration, and (e) participation [28,31].

Local e-government initiatives can be found in almost all the modernization programs of Western democracies [24]. In the twenty-first century, local governments worldwide are under pressure to change and innovate the way in which their bureaucracies interact with citizens.

Several studies provides an overall view about the use of new information and communication technologies (ICT) by municipalities to determine whether local governments are using these technologies to increase transparency and e-participation, opening a real corporate dialogue. Studies in United States [32], Finland [33,34], Estonia [35], Denmark [36], The Netherlands [37,38], Spain [8,39] explore the adoption and implementation of e-government initiatives at local level and discuss the main barriers and opportunities occurring in the interaction between municipalities and citizens. However, few studies identify those factors that promote the level of development of e-government initiatives at local level [40,41]. Municipal population was the only explanatory variable that was studied on more than one study [42–45].

Finally, it should be noted that, although there is a large literature focused on the study of local e-government initiatives [1,7,29,32,40], the implementation of interaction mechanisms between Portuguese municipalities and society is little studied. Thus, for example, Silva et al. [10] analyze the use of social networks (Facebook activity) by local governments in Portugal; Fedotova et al. (2013) evaluate the Web 2.0 infrastructures of Portuguese local governments and citizens' adherence to the applications present in their official portals; Paiva-Dias and Costa [46] analyze the websites of Portuguese municipalities according to three dimensions: government information, e-service and participation; and Naranjo-Zolotov et al. [9] analyze electronic platforms for participatory budgeting.

2.2. Theoretical framework

The need to provide dynamic channels of participation and information in the field of public administration using technological communication devices can be examined based on different theories. Firstly, the public accountability perspective suggests that rulers are intrinsically trustworthy and have a greater commitment to public accountability and transparency, so they are more likely to participate in the implementation of transparency systems in municipalities and, therefore, in the voluntary disclosure of information to citizens [96].

Legitimacy theory examines the actions undertaken by managers, usually through information disclosure, aimed to change the perception of government to increase the legitimacy of its actions and its existence. According to predictions based on legitimacy theory [47,48], improving citizen participation processes, as well as increasing voluntary information disclosure, can be a strategic means by which politicians can demonstrate the congruence of their goals and norms with those held by society [49]. This has positive consequences for institutional reputation, image and public goodwill. From this perspective, greater transparency and improved channels for citizen participation in municipal management would strengthen the legitimacy of politicians.

Thirdly, following the stakeholder theory [50], it is essential that managers consider the opinion of the social actors with which the institution is related - stakeholders or interest groups - and that the

decisions made by the municipality are advantageous to all. Thus, stakeholder theory postulates that stakeholders, both internal and external, have the right to access information on the activities and results obtained by local governments [51,52]. Local governments are obliged to meet citizens' demand for greater participation in decisions that affect them, as well as greater oversight and accountability. Providing information online allows citizens to satisfy their information needs and be aware of the value creation process. This can create a good relationship with different stakeholders, such as citizens, funding agencies, national and regional government, employers and employees, facilitating their support and approval [53].

In the field of public management, this theory is directly related to the theory of social responsibility. This theory promotes that public institutions be responsible for their actions and take into account their impact on society. To achieve this, they must be more transparent and sustainable according to the new economic-social context [54]. The relationship with stakeholders is directly associated with the municipality's strategic planning. Planning requires the establishing of participation mechanisms to know the expectations and needs of the community and to satisfy them, subsequently establishing information channels to bring stakeholders closer to the degree of achievement of the objectives set.

The relationship with stakeholders has a triple objective [55]: to collect information that supports decision making, to create a participatory dynamic so that stakeholders feel part of the institution, and to develop the level of relationship so that stakeholders move from a passive to a participatory position. According to this theory, governors make decisions that are regulated, collaborated, guided, legitimized and inspected by some influential stakeholders that need to be considered in their performance management [56].

Fourthly, from the perspective of agency theory [57–59], a higher level of information reduces informational asymmetries, reducing the potential conflict of interest between citizens and politicians, increasing the degree of trust. From this perspective, as highlighted by White et al. [60]; the voluntary disclosure of information online may represent a valid attempt to reduce political costs. This agency relationship between citizens and public administrations is more important the closer the services are provided to citizens, where the demand for participation and the information needs of citizens increase. This is particularly true in the case of local governments, where citizens' demands for access to information from the administration become more intense [61], especially of aspects beyond those traditionally demanded in financial statements. Based on this theory, the importance of introducing higher transparency and dynamic channels of citizen participation in local governments is increasingly growing. These requirements condition governments to be more effective and efficient, with the add value of being accountable to citizens and facilitating their participation in public life [62].

2.3. Development of hypotheses

In addition to the mentioned theories, we consider that the size of the municipality could condition, in a positive way, the levels of transparency of local governments, having special incidence in the application of these theories. A larger population size implies a greater number of users of public services and the management of larger amounts of public funds. Therefore, governments are under greater pressure to act responsibly, increasing the need for accountability and transparency [11–14,59,63–65].

The larger the population, the greater the need to channel participation and information in order to achieve greater legitimacy of those in power and unite their interests with those of the citizens. This can be explained by the pressure of a greater volume of users of public services [11], by the desire to reduce political costs through citizen control [63] or by a greater need for information among the population living in larger territories [66].

The next issue is the culture, habits and needs. Inhabitants of small municipalities trust public authorities more often, but prefer personal contacts with the office, which gives them greater satisfaction and a sense of participating in the life of their commune [67]. In large municipalities, relations are more anonymous, hence more formalized contacts are preferred and it is necessary to study the needs of their inhabitants [68,69].

Previous empirical studies have evidenced a positive relationship between municipality size and the extent of e-government adoption [70–72]. Specifically, some studies have shown that larger municipalities tend to create a website more frequently than their smaller counterparts to maintain e-information (Musso et al., 2000; [12,14,44, 73–76]). However, this positive relationship is not contrasted in all the studies conducted. For example, some studies show that population size is not a predictor of online information diffusion [11]; García et al., 2016; [59,77], while Da Costa et al. [78] found an inverse relationship.

In the other hand, some studies found that larger cities are more likely to offer online public services [45,79–81]. Likewise, other studies [75,80,82] have shown that the development of e-participation is higher in larger municipalities. Finally, Ingrams et al. [40] evidenced that population size has a positive association with higher e-information, e-services and e-participation development from 80 global cities.

Taking these approaches into account and with the aim of answering our three research questions - Are municipalities committed and involved in promoting online interaction initiatives? Are these mechanisms improving over time? What is the influence of the size of municipalities on the development of online citizen interaction initiatives? - we formulate the following hypotheses:

H1. Municipalities are committed to developing online initiatives for citizen participation.

H2. Municipalities are improving and increasing citizen participation mechanisms over the years.

H3. There are significant differences in the implementation of online citizen participation initiatives depending on the population size of the municipality.

H4. The size of the municipalities has a positive and significant influence on the development of initiatives and mechanisms related to information available to citizens and society.

H5. The size of municipalities has a positive and significant influence on the development of initiatives and mechanisms related to interaction with citizens and society.

3. Context of Portuguese local government

Portugal is one of the European countries that has been a pioneer in regulating access to public information. Since 1989, the Portuguese Constitution has established the principle of “open administration” (Article 268.2), granting citizens the right of access to administrative files and records, except for matters relating to internal and external security or relating to citizens’ personal data. This constitutional principle was subsequently regulated by Law 65/1993, which established the conditions for access to administrative information. In 2016, Law 26/2016, of August 22 was passed, introducing active disclosure of information on the operation and control of activities, to ensure transparency of administrative activities and dissemination of information by encouraging the use of the Internet.

Portuguese local governments have introduced mechanisms to promote the disclosure of information and citizen participation through their websites. In Portugal, there are 278 municipalities on the mainland and 30 in the two Atlantic archipelagos. The Portuguese Constitution established three levels of government: administrative regions, municipalities and parishes (*freguesias*). Administrative regions have not yet been implemented in mainland Portugal. The only two autonomous

regions are the Atlantic archipelagos: the Azores and Madeira. Local governments include municipalities and parishes. Each municipality includes several parishes. The parishes are the lowest administrative unit, have a very limited scope of competencies and resources, and are the link between the municipality and the needs of the population.

It is important to highlight that Portugal has a high e-government development index. The e-government ranking is published biannually by the Department of Economic and Social Affairs of the United Nations (UN) and is composed of three elements: 1) availability of online services, 2) telecommunications infrastructure and 3) human capacity. This ranking indicates that by 2020 Portugal is on the list of countries with a very high EGDI (E-Government Development Index) (0.8255). Portugal ranks 35th in the global list of 193 countries [98]. On the other hand, the report published in 2020 includes a specific indicator of the local level, LOSI (Local Online Service Index), where 100 local entities worldwide have been included, among them, from Portugal, only Lisbon has been analyzed, which has obtained a high LOSI result of 0.55, occupying the 26th position.

In this context of e-government development, Portuguese municipalities are an interesting scenario to explore the implementation of online initiatives for citizen interaction because Portugal is a country that is developing its own open government strategy, and this is expected to influence the mechanisms that municipalities develop in order to interact with citizens. In addition, the large number of Portuguese municipalities, which are governed by the same legal rules, and the diversity of them, with respect to their population size, brings an important advantage in order to explore whether the citizen participation initiatives that are adopted in Portuguese municipalities are conditioned by the size of the population. In fact, the pressures exerted by the citizens of the municipality may lead to a greater development of online citizen participation initiatives. These are the reasons that lead us to study municipalities in Portugal.

4. Research methodology

In order to explore the citizen participation initiatives implemented by Portuguese municipalities over time, and to determine the possible influence of the size of the municipalities in the adoption of electronic initiatives of citizen participation, we conducted a descriptive analysis of the evolution over time of the initiatives and mechanisms related to citizen interaction and society in relation to the size of the municipalities. Secondly, with the application of a univariate and bivariate analysis we have studied the existence of significant differences over time and according to population size. Finally, by means of a panel data regression using random effects we have corroborated the influence of population size on the development and implementation of citizen participation initiatives by Portuguese municipalities.

4.1. Sample, variables and data collection

The population under study is focused on 308 municipalities for 3 years (2015, 2016 and 2017). Those observations with missing data were discarded. We have worked with an unbalanced data panel of 803 observations (municipality-year). Given the large number of Portuguese municipalities and the considerable differences between them with respect to their size, we have adopted our own classification criterion based on the classification established by INE and the Financial Yearbook (see Table 1).

For this study, and in order to answer the research questions, we have distributed the municipalities according to 5 population groups. The distribution of the sample for each of the population brackets is very similar except for those municipalities with less than 5000 inhabitants, as shown in Table 2.

The final sample used in this study consists of 803 municipalities in Portugal for the period 2015–2017. Thus, 91 municipalities have less than 5000 inhabitants with an average value of 3646 inhabitants; 195

Table 1
Classification established by the INE and the Financial Yearbook.

INE-OCDE		Financial Yearbook	
Predominantly rural	Population less than 2000 inhabitants	Small	Population less than 20,000 inhabitants
Semi-urban	Population between 2000 and 5000 inhabitants	Medium	Population between 20,000 and 100,000 inhabitants
Urban	Population of 5000 inhabitants or more	Large	Population of 100,000 inhabitants or more

Source: INE y Financial Yearbook

municipalities have between 5000 and 10,000 inhabitants with an average population of 7070 inhabitants; 185 municipalities are included in the segment between 10,000 and 20,000 inhabitants with an average of 15,320 inhabitants; 171 municipalities have between 20,000 and 50,000 inhabitants with a value in the average population of 30,707; and, finally, 161 municipalities larger than 50,000 inhabitants with an average 117,936 inhabitants.

Next, and based on a selection of indicators from the transparency index of Portuguese municipalities (see <https://transparencia.pt/itm/>), we have identified the initiatives and mechanisms related to the processes and channels of participation through the municipal web. In this sense, we have identified these initiatives and mechanisms according to: a) those related to the information available to citizens and society (see Table 3), and b) those related to the interaction with citizens and society (see Table 4). Thus, a categorical content analysis is performed by designing a codebook from the selection of indicators (initiatives and mechanisms) identifying whether the municipality has such indicator or not [83]. And finally, this content analysis has enabled the development of two disclosure indexes that are quantitative indicators that allow quantifying initiatives related to information available to citizens and society (municipal information index) and initiatives related to interaction with citizens and society (municipal interaction index).

Table 3 shows the initiatives and mechanisms related to information available to citizens and society, together with their description and measurement. In this sense, we have analyzed whether the municipality has: (i) search engine on the municipality’s website; (ii) municipal information system (updated information on interruptions, suspensions or alterations in services, roads and public transport networks); (iii) publication of operating hours of the municipality, its services and equipment; (iv) publication of protocols and resolutions on subsidies, use of movable property, such as vehicles, and real estate for civic, sports, cultural, recreational or other associations.

Table 4 shows the initiatives and mechanisms related to interaction with citizens and society. We have studied whether the municipality has: (i) municipal ombudsman (publication of statute and contact); (ii) link/s to social networks with activity; (iii) information request service that allows citizens to follow the administrative procedure online; (iv) channel for complaints/suggestions.

In order to quantify the information related to the online implementation of transparency initiatives as well as citizen participation mechanisms, we have elaborated disclosure indexes that are widely used

Table 2
Distribution of the sample (municipalities) according to the size of the population and the year under study.

Population (inhabitants)	2015			2016			2017			2015–2017		
	N	%	mean									
<5000	30	11.2	3668	30	11.2	3668	31	11.6	3604	91	11.3	3646
≥5000; <10,000	65	24.3	7089	65	24.3	7089	65	24.3	7034	195	24.3	7070
≥10,000; <20,000	62	23.1	14,318	62	23.1	14,318	61	22.8	14,324	185	23.0	14,320
≥20,000; <50,000	57	21.3	30,635	57	21.3	30,635	57	21.3	30,853	171	21.3	30,707
≥50,000	54	20.1	117,500	54	20.1	117,500	53	19.9	118,825	161	20.0	117,936
Total	268	100	35,633	268	100	35,633	267	100	35,577	803	100	35,615

Source: own elaboration

as an established method in the social sciences [84]. Two unweighted indexes were elaborated, as specified below:

$$\text{Municipal Information Index}_j = \frac{1}{4} \sum_{i=1}^4 X_{ij} \tag{1}$$

$$\text{Municipal Participation Index}_j = \frac{1}{4} \sum_{i=1}^4 X_{ij} \tag{2}$$

where the Municipal Information Index_j and the Municipal Interaction Index_j are the absolute unweighted information and interaction indexes for municipality; *j*, *i* are the indicators or items, and X_{ij} is the score obtained for indicator *i* for municipality *j*. Thus, X_{ij} will take the value 1 if municipality *j* has indicator or item *i*, and will take the value 0 otherwise.

The information index is a useful tool for measuring the level of transparency that Portuguese municipalities present to citizens and society. Its usefulness lies in the fact that it makes possible to analyze the information culture of the municipalities. Thus, depending on how municipalities incorporate relevant information about initiatives and mechanisms related to information available to citizens and society on their websites (Table 3), there will be an increase in the level of useful and important information made available to citizens and society. These actions will contribute to increasing the level of useful and important information offer to citizens and society.

The interaction index provides an assessment of the existence and functioning of formal mechanisms for citizen participation. The higher the value of the index, the greater the number of instruments implemented in municipalities to improve citizen participation.

The availability of these indexes contributes to understand the level of municipal openness to citizens, which may contribute to improve citizens’ participation in those matters that affect them. A high value of these indexes may represent greater empowerment of citizens, as they indicate that the municipality is promoting greater participation in local life, thus contributing to the improvement of the quality of democracy.

4.2. Study period

The period analyzed covers 3 years, from 2015 to 2017 (both inclusive). This choice is because of these are the years in which the information related to the Portuguese municipal transparency index is broken down. This information is our source for data collection.

4.3. Statistical processing

After data collection, and with the aim of being able to contrast the research hypotheses that we have proposed, we have carried out the following statistical strategy.

In order to know the behavior of the variables, we have obtained the frequencies throughout the different years and by dimension of the municipality, since they are dummy variables that take the value 1 or 0. Thus, we have obtained a basic knowledge of the main indicators related to the implementation of processes and channels for the dissemination of information, as well as processes for participation through the websites

Table 3
Initiatives and mechanisms related to information available to citizens and society.

INITIATIVES AND MECHANISMS	DESCRIPTION	MEASURING
Search engine on the municipality’s website (i)	Analyze whether the municipality has a search engine on the municipality’s website, where it is possible to search by key words the content of the website.	1 available 0 not available
Municipal information system (ii)	Analyze whether relevant information is made available to citizens regarding issues that affect their daily life and relationship with municipal services, such as traffic interruptions, power and water outages, etc.	1 available 0 not available
Publication of operating hours of the municipality, its services and equipment (iii)	Analyze whether the municipality has information on the opening hours of the town hall, service desks, libraries, pavilions and other municipal services and facilities.	1 available 0 not available
Publication of protocols and resolutions on subsidies, use of movable property, such as vehicles, and real estate for civic, sports, cultural, recreational or other associations (iv)	Analyze whether the collaboration protocols signed with other entities are available in the municipality, as well as the deliberations of the City Council meetings where it has been decided to offer some type of support (monetary, transfer of assets or otherwise). This information should be available for at least the last year. Alternatively, a list (“subsidy map”) may be made available with the benefits granted annually to municipal associations, the preparation and publication of which is mandatory under Law 64/2013 of August 27. The information provided must identify the beneficiary, have information on the amount transferred or the amount and nature of the benefit granted, the date of the decision, the purpose of the support and the legal basis.	1 available 0 not available

Source: Own elaboration based on the transparency index of Portuguese municipalities (<https://transparencia.pt/itm/>)

of Portuguese municipalities. In addition, information is obtained on the importance of each of the variables evaluated. Additionally, to analyze the existence of significant differences over the years we have applied the Pearson’s chi square test of independence. In the same way, we have identify the existence of significant differences for each of the population segments in the period 2015–2017 for the Portuguese municipalities.

In addition, the main measures of trend, dispersion and distribution were obtained for the two disclosure indexes. We have also analyzed the existence of significant differences over the years in these indexes and in the different population dimensions over the period under study.

Finally, four univariate regressions have been applied for each of the disclosure indexes, where the dependent variable is the index and the independent variable is the size of the municipality. Panel data methodology techniques have been used to estimate the models (pooled regression, fixed effects regression, random effects regression and random effects regression with robust errors) and several tests have been obtained (the Breusch-Pagan Lagrange test, the F test and the Hausman test) in order to detect the most robust model, in our case random effects. Likewise, the models have also been estimated considering the variable size of the municipality by population segments.

Table 4
Initiatives and mechanisms related to interaction with citizens and society.

INITIATIVES AND MECHANISMS	DESCRIPTION	MEASURING
Municipal ombudsman (publication of statute and contact)	Analyze whether the municipality has a statute and contact an independent figure, whose function is to guarantee the rights and legitimate interests of the citizens before the municipal bodies, providing a channel of interrelation.	1 available 0 not available
Link/s to social networks with activity	Analyze whether the municipality has links to online social networks such as Facebook, Twitter or Youtube. These networks should be operational and up to date.	1 available 0 not available
Information request service that allows citizens to follow the administrative procedure online	Analyze whether citizens can request information from municipal services on administrative procedures or on their relationship with the municipal administration.	1 available 0 not available
Channel for complaints/suggestions	Analyze whether the municipality’s website has its own platform that allows citizens to make complaints or suggestions for improvement of public services.	1 available 0 not available

Source: Own elaboration based on the transparency index of Portuguese municipalities (<https://transparencia.pt/itm/>)

The statistical techniques used have been estimated with the STATA 16.1 software.

5. Results analysis

5.1. Initiatives and mechanisms related to information available to citizens and society

Table 5 shows the frequencies of the initiatives related to the existence of a search engine, the existence of information system, the existence of the publication of operating hours of the municipality and the existence of the publication of protocols and resolutions on subsidies and use of real estate by associations. We can observe that for the period 2015–2017 93.3% of the municipalities have a search engine on their websites, inferior is the existence of information systems and the publication of operating hours of the municipality, since only 66.6% and 68.7%, respectively have implemented these initiatives in their municipalities. In addition, only 54.4% of the municipalities publish protocols and resolutions on subsidies and use of movable property by associations. Furthermore, for the period under study, significant differences are observed in the implementation of these initiatives depending on the

Table 5
Frequencies of initiatives and mechanisms related to information available to citizens and society on the municipal web by size and year.

	2015			2016			2017			$X^2_{(2)}(p\text{-value})$	2015–2017			$X^2_{(4)}(p\text{-value})$
	No(%)	Yes(%)	Total	No(%)	Yes(%)	Total	No(%)	Yes(%)	Total		No(%)	Yes(%)	Total	
Panel A: Search engine on the municipality's website														
<5000	6 (20%)	24 (80%)	30	3 (10%)	27 (90%)	30	4 (12,9%)	27 (87,1%)	31	1.30 (0.52)	13 (14,3%)	78 (85,7%)	91	11.36 (0.02)**
≥5000; <10,000	6 (9.2%)	59 (90.8%)	65	5 (7.7%)	60 (92.3%)	65	4 (6,2%)	61 (93,8%)	65	0.43 (0.81)	15 (7,7%)	180 (92,3%)	195	
≥10,000; <20,000	6 (9.7%)	56 (90.3%)	62	3 (4.8%)	59 (95.2%)	62	2 (3,3%)	59 (96,7%)	61	2.46 (0.29)	11 (5,9%)	174 (94,1%)	185	
≥20,000; <50,000	4 (7%)	53 (93%)	57	3 (5,3%)	54 (94,7%)	57	1 (1,8%)	56 (98,2%)	57	1.84 (0.40)	8 (4,7%)	163 (95,3%)	171	
≥50,000	3 (5.6%)	51 (94.4%)	54	2 (3.7%)	52 (96.3%)	54	2 (3,8%)	51 (96,2%)	53	0.29 (0.87)	7 (4,4%)	154 (95,6%)	161	
Total	25(9.3%)	243(90.7%)	268	16(6%)	252(94%)	268	13(4.9%)	254(95.1%)	267	4.61(0.10)	54(6.7%)	749(93.3%)	803	
Panel B: Municipal information system														
<5000	18 (60%)	12 (40%)	30	13 (43.3%)	17 (56.7%)	30	13 (42%)	18 (58%)	31	2.44 (0.30)	44 (48.3%)	47 (51.7%)	91	51.60 (0.00)***
≥5000; <10,000	33 (50.8%)	32 (49.2%)	65	27 (41.5%)	38 (58.5%)	65	34 (52.3%)	31 (47.7%)	65	1.77 (0.41)	94 (48.2%)	101 (51.8%)	195	
≥10,000; <20,000	24 (38.7%)	38 (61.3%)	62	15 (24.2%)	47 (75.8%)	62	15 (24.6%)	46 (75.4%)	61	4.10 (0.13)	54 (29.2%)	131 (70.9%)	185	
≥20,000; <50,000	18 (31.6%)	39 (68.4%)	57	13 (22.8%)	44 (77.2%)	57	18 (31.6%)	39 (68.4%)	57	1.43 (0.49)	49 (28.7%)	122 (71.3%)	171	
≥50,000	12 (22.2%)	42 (77.8%)	54	7 (13%)	47 (87%)	54	8 (15.1%)	45 (84.9%)	53	1.82 (0.40)	27 (16.8%)	134 (83.2%)	161	
Total	105(39.2%)	163(60.8%)	268	75(28%)	193(72%)	268	88(33%)	179(67%)	267	7.58(0.02)**	268(33.4%)	535(66.6%)	803	
Panel C: Publication of operating hours of the municipality, its services and equipment														
<5000	19 (63.3%)	11 (36.7%)	30	13 (43.3%)	17 (56.7%)	30	12 (38.7%)	19 (61.3%)	31	4.15 (0.13)	44 (48.4%)	47 (51.6%)	91	27.15 (0.00)***
≥5000; <10,000	31 (47.7%)	34 (52.3%)	65	23 (35.4%)	42 (64.6%)	65	22 (33.9%)	43 (66.1%)	65	3.15 (0.21)	76 (39%)	119 (61%)	195	
≥10,000; <20,000	16 (25.8%)	46 (74.2%)	62	16 (25.8%)	46 (74.2%)	62	19 (31.6%)	42 (68.4%)	61	0.58 (0.75)	51 (27.6%)	134 (72.4%)	185	
≥20,000; <50,000	11 (19.3%)	46 (80.7%)	57	10 (17.5%)	47 (82.5%)	57	18 (31.6%)	39 (68.4%)	57	3.79 (0.15)	39 (22.8%)	132 (77.2%)	171	
≥50,000	10 (18.5%)	44 (81.5%)	54	15 (27.8%)	39 (72.2%)	54	16 (30.2%)	37 (69.8%)	53	2.15 (0.34)	41 (25.5%)	120 (74.5%)	161	
Total	87(32.5%)	181(67.5%)	268	77(28.7%)	191(71.3%)	268	87(32.6%)	180(67.4%)	267	1.20(0.55)	251(31.3%)	552(68.7%)	803	
Publication of protocols and resolutions on subsidies, use of movable property, such as vehicles, and real estate for civic, sports, cultural, recreational or other associations														
<5000	17 (56.7%)	13 (43.3%)	30	15 (50%)	15 (50%)	30	22 (71%)	9 (29%)	31	2.91 (0.23)	54 (59.3%)	37 (40.6%)	91	17.79 (0.00)***
≥5000; <10,000	36 (55.4%)	29 (44.6%)	65	29 (44.6%)	36 (55.4%)	65	34 (52.3%)	31 (47.7%)	65	1.60 (0.45)	99 (50.8%)	96 (49.2%)	195	
≥10,000; <20,000	30 (48.4%)	32 (51.6%)	62	21 (33.9%)	41 (66.1%)	62	37 (60.7%)	24 (39.3%)	61	8.87 (0.01)**	88 (47.6%)	97 (52.4%)	185	
≥20,000; <50,000	23 (40.4%)	34 (59.6%)	57	19 (33.3%)	38 (66.7%)	57	23 (40.4%)	34 (59.6%)	57	0.79 (0.67)	65 (38%)	106 (62%)	171	
≥50,000	21 (38.9%)	33 (61.1%)	54	16 (29.6%)	38 (70.4%)	54	23 (43.4%)	30 (56.6%)	53	2.26 (0.32)	60 (37.3%)	101 (62.7%)	161	
Total	127(47.4%)	141(52.6%)	268	100(37.3%)	168(62.7%)	268	139(52.1%)	128(47.9%)	267	12.26(0.00)***	366(45.6%)	437(54.4%)	803	

p-value: ***1%, **5%, *10%.

Source: Own elaboration

Table 6
Descriptive statistics of the municipal information index by size and year.

Population (inhabitants)	Information Index																	
	2015			2016			2017			2015–2017			X ₍₂₎ ²			X ₍₄₎ ²		
	Md.	Dv.	Mn.	Md.	Dv.	Mn.	Md.	Dv.	Mn.	Md.	Dv.	Mn.	Md.	Dv.	Mn.	Md.	Dv.	Mn.
<5000	50.00	25.43	0	63.33	24.33	25	58.87	20.96	100	57.42	24.01	0	4.61	20.96	100	57.42	24.01	0
≥5000; <10,000	59.23	25.22	0	67.69	26.78	25	63.85	24.22	100	63.59	25.53	0	2.63	24.22	100	63.59	25.53	0
≥10,000; <20,000	69.35	21.43	25	77.82	23.57	25	70.08	21.80	100	72.43	22.50	25	12.46***	21.80	100	72.43	22.50	25
≥20,000; <50,000	75.44	25.22	0	80.26	22.53	25	73.68	20.82	100	76.46	22.96	0	4.59	20.82	100	76.46	22.96	0
≥50,000	78.70	21.94	25	81.48	18.29	25	76.89	22.39	100	79.04	20.90	25	0.04	22.39	100	79.04	20.90	25
Total	67.91	25.44	0	75.00	24.09	25	69.38	22.87	100	70.77	24.32	0	14.70***	22.87	100	70.77	24.32	0

Note: Md: mean, Dv: standard deviation, Mx: maximum, Mn: minimum. p-value: ***1%, **5%, *10%. Source: Own elaboration

size of the population ($X_4^2 = 11.36$, p-value = 0.02; $X_4^2 = 51.60$, p-value = 0.00; $X_4^2 = 27.15$, p-value = 0.00; $X_4^2 = 17.79$, p-value = 0.00, respectively), with the largest municipalities implementing the most initiatives.

Over the years, the initiatives and mechanisms of information transparency implemented by Portuguese municipalities have increased. Initiatives related to the existence of information systems and to the publication of protocols and resolutions on subsidies and use of movable assets by associations on a global basis are those that have experienced a significant difference over the years ($X_2^2 = 7.58$, p-value = 0.02; $X_2^2 = 12.26$, p-value = 0.00, respectively). Additionally, municipalities with between 10,000 and 20,000 inhabitants are those that have experienced the most significant differences over the years in relation to the implementation of mechanisms and initiatives related to the publication of protocols and resolutions on grants and use of movable property by associations ($X_2^2 = 8.87$, p-value = 0.01).

5.1.1. Municipal information index

Table 6 shows the descriptive statistics of the municipal information index that has been elaborated in relation to the mean, standard deviation and the maximum and minimum value of the index. In addition, we observe that there are significant differences over the years in relation to this index globally ($X_2^2 = 14.70$, p-value = 0.00) and, specifically, in those municipalities with a population between 10,000 and 20,000 inhabitants ($X_2^2 = 12.46$, p-value = 0.00). Likewise, for the period from 2015 to 2017, significant differences according to population size were identified ($X_4^2 = 37.39$, p-value = 0.00).

5.2. Initiatives and mechanisms related to interaction with citizens and society

Table 7 shows the frequencies related to the existence of links to social networks with activity, the existence of information service for online administrative procedures, the existence of an ombudsman with publication of the statute and contact, and the existence of a forum for suggestions/complaints. Thus, for the period 2015–2017 we observe that 89.7% of Portuguese municipalities have developed initiatives related to the existence of links to social networks with activity and 66.9% have a space for complaints and suggestions. However, only 38.4% of the municipalities in Portugal have implemented an online information service for administrative procedures. In addition, 5.1% have a public ombudsman with a published statute and contact information. For this period, significant differences are identified in the implementation of these initiatives depending on the size of the population ($X_4^2 = 18.86$, p-value = 0.00; $X_4^2 = 84.17$, p-value = 0.00; $X_4^2 = 28.39$, p-value = 0.00, respectively), except for the case of initiatives related to the existence of an ombudsman with publication of the statute and contact that no significant differences were found ($X_4^2 = 3.09$, p-value = 0.54).

Likewise, over the years, the initiatives and mechanisms implemented by the municipalities to improve the participation of society in the management of the municipality and in the services that affect them have increased. The initiatives related to the existence of links to social networks with activity, the existence of the information service for online administrative procedures and the existence of an ombudsman with publication of the statute and contact globally have experienced a significant difference over the years ($X_2^2 = 13.32$, p-value = 0.00; $X_2^2 = 6.20$, p-value = 0.05; $X_2^2 = 14.95$, p-value = 0.00, respectively). Additionally, municipalities with between 10,000 and 20,000 inhabitants have significant differences over the years regarding the implementation of mechanisms and initiatives related to the existence of links to social networks with activity ($X_2^2 = 11.60$, p-value = 0.00).

5.2.1. Municipal participation index

Table 8 shows the descriptive statistics of the municipal interaction index that has been elaborated in relation to the mean, standard

Table 7
Frequencies of initiatives and mechanisms related to interaction with citizens and society on the municipal website by size and year.

Population (inhabitants)	2015			2016			2017			$X^2_{(2)}(p\text{-value})$	2015–2017			$X^2_{(4)}(p\text{-value})$
	No(%)	Yes(%)	Total	Yes(%)	Yes(%)	Total	Yes(%)	Si(%)	Total		No(%)	Yes(%)	Total	
Panel A: Link/s to social networks with activity														
<5000	7 (23.3%)	23 (76.7%)	30	5 (16.7%)	25 (83.3%)	30	3 (9.7%)	28 (90.3%)	31	2.10 (0.36)	15 (16.5%)	76 (83.52%)	91	18.86 (0.00)***
≥5000; <10,000	16 (24.6%)	49 (75.4%)	65	9 (13.8%)	56 (86.2%)	65	7 (10.8%)	58 (89.2%)	65	5.01 (0.08)*	32 (16.4%)	163 (83.6%)	195	
≥10,000; <20,000	10 (16.1%)	52 (83.9%)	62	4 (6.5%)	58 (93.5%)	62	61 (100%)	–	61	11.60 (0.00)***	14 (7.6%)	171 (92.4%)	185	
≥20,000; <50,000	6 (10.5%)	51 (89.5%)	57	4 (7%)	53 (93%)	57	4 (7%)	53 (93%)	57	0.62 (0.73)	14 (8.2%)	157 (91.9)	171	
≥50,000	3 (5.6%)	51 (94.4%)	54	2 (3.7%)	52 (96.3%)	54	3 (5.7%)	50 (94.3%)	53	0.28 (0.87)	8 (5%)	153 (95%)	161	
Total	42(15.7%)	226(84.3%)	268	24(9%)	244(91%)	268	17(6.4%)	250(93.6%)	267	13.32(0.00)***	83(10.3%)	720(89.7%)	803	
Panel B: Information request service that allows citizens to follow the administrative procedure online														
<5000	28 (93.3%)	2 (6.7%)	30	22 (73.3%)	8 (26.7%)	30	25 (80.7%)	6 (19.3%)	31	4.24 (0.12)	75 (82.4%)	16 (17.6%)	91	84.17 (0.00)***
≥5000; <10,000	58 (89.2%)	7 (10.8%)	65	50 (77%)	15 (23%)	65	46 (70.8%)	19 (29.2%)	65	6.92 (0.03)**	154 (79%)	41 (21%)	195	
≥10,000; <20,000	39 (62.9%)	23 (37.1%)	62	35 (56.5%)	27 (43.5%)	62	35 (57.4%)	26 (42.6%)	61	0.62 (0.73)	109 (59%)	76 (41%)	185	
≥20,000; <50,000	33 (57.9%)	24 (42.1%)	57	28 (49.1%)	29 (50.9%)	57	36 (63.2%)	21 (36.8%)	57	2.33 (0.31)	97 (56.7%)	74 (43.3)	171	
≥50,000	21 (38.9%)	33 (61.1%)	54	16 (29.6%)	38 (70.4%)	54	23 (43.4%)	30 (56.6%)	53	2.26 (0.32)	60 (37.3%)	101 (62.7%)	161	
Total	179(66.8%)	89(33.2%)	268	151(56.3%)	117(43.6%)	268	165(61.8%)	102(38.2%)	267	6.20(0.05)**	495(61.6%)	308(38.4%)	803	
Panel C: Information request service that allows citizens to follow the administrative procedure online														
<5000	29 (96.7%)	1 (3.3%)	30	26 (86.7%)	4 (13.3%)	30	30 (96.8%)	1 (3.2%)	31	3.30 (0.19)	85 (93.4%)	6 (6.6%)	91	3.09 (0.54)
≥5000; <10,000	64 (98.5%)	1 (1.5%)	65	61 (93.8%)	4 (6.2%)	65	64 (98.5%)	1 (1.5%)	65	3.10 (0.21)	189 (96.9%)	6 (3.1%)	195	
≥10,000; <20,000	60 (96.8%)	2 (3.2%)	62	56 (90.3%)	6 (9.7%)	62	60 (98.4%)	1 (1.6%)	61	4.83 (0.09)*	176 (95.1%)	9 (4.9%)	185	
≥20,000; <50,000	55 (96.5%)	2 (3.5%)	57	52 (91.2%)	5 (8.8%)	57	55 (96.5%)	2 (3.5%)	57	2.11 (0.35)	162 (94.7%)	9 (5.3%)	171	
≥50,000	51 (94.4%)	3 (5.6%)	54	48 (88.9%)	6 (11.1%)	54	51 (96.2%)	2 (3.8%)	53	2.47 (0.29)	150 (93.2%)	11 (6.8%)	161	
Total	259(96.6%)	9(3.4%)	268	243(90.7%)	25(9.3%)	268	260(97.4%)	7(2.6%)	267	14.95(0.00)***	762(94.9%)	41(5.1%)	803	
Panel D: Channel for complaints/suggestions														
<5000	14 (46.7%)	16 (53.3%)	30	14 (46.7%)	16 (53.3%)	30	17 (54.8%)	14 (45.2%)	31	0.55 (0.76)	45 (49.5%)	46 (50.5%)	91	28.39 (0.00)***
≥5000; <10,000	23 (35.4%)	42 (64.6%)	65	23 (35.4%)	42 (64.6%)	65	28 (43.1%)	37 (56.9%)	65	1.09 (0.58)	74 (38%)	121 (62%)	195	
≥10,000; <20,000	25 (40.3%)	37 (59.7%)	62	21 (33.8%)	41 (66.1%)	62	23 (37.7%)	38 (62.3%)	61	0.56 (0.76)	69 (37.3%)	116 (62.7%)	185	
≥20,000; <50,000	15 (26.3%)	42 (73.7%)	57	13 (22.8%)	44 (77.2%)	57	13 (22.8%)	44 (77.2%)	57	0.26 (0.88)	41 (24%)	130 (76%)	171	
≥50,000	10 (18.5%)	44 (81.5%)	54	11 (20.4%)	43 (79.6%)	54	16 (30.2%)	37 (69.8%)	53	2.37 (0.31)	37 (23%)	124 (77%)	161	
Total	87(32.5%)	181(67.5%)	268	82(30.6%)	186(69.4%)	268	97(36.3%)	170(63.7%)	267	2.06(0.36)	266(33.1%)	537(66.9%)	803	

p-value: ***1%, **5%, *10%.

Source: Own elaboration

Table 8
Descriptive statistics of the municipal interaction index by size and year.

Population (inhabitants)	Participation Index															
	2015			2016			2017			2015–2017			$\bar{X}_{(4)}$			
	Md.	Dv.	Mn.	Md.	Dv.	Mn.	Md.	Dv.	Mn.	Md.	Dv.	Mn.				
<5000	35.00	24.21	0	44.17	28.38	0	39.52	22.15	0	100	5.72*	39.56	25.02	0	100	74.50***
≥5000; <10,000	38.08	19.82	0	45.00	23.88	0	44.23	21.55	0	100	4.29	42.44	21.92	0	100	
≥10,000; <20,000	45.97	23.17	0	53.23	22.85	0	51.64	20.35	25	100	1.44	50.27	22.27	0	100	
≥20,000; <50,000	52.19	21.79	0	57.46	19.46	25	52.63	19.87	0	100	1.11	54.09	20.42	0	100	
≥50,000	60.65	18.56	25	64.35	19.79	25	56.13	22.42	0	100	3.55	60.40	20.46	0	100	
Total	47.11	22.97	0	53.36	23.56	0	49.53	21.73	0	100	8.43**	50.00	22.88	0	100	

Note: Md: mean, Dv: standard deviation, Mx: maximum, Mn: minimum. p-value: ***1%, **5%, *10%. Source: Own elaboration

deviation and the maximum and minimum value of this index. In addition, we observe that there are significant differences over the years in relation to this index globally ($X_2^2 = 8.43$, p-value = 0.02) and, specifically, in those municipalities with a population of less than 5000 inhabitants ($X_2^2 = 5.72$, p-value = 0.06). Likewise, for the period 2015–2017 we identified significant differences according to population size ($X_4^2 = 74.50$, p-value = 0.00).

5.3. Panel data regression

Table 9 shows the results of the panel data regression. We have obtained different tests in order to determine the most robust estimation. The Breusch-Pagan Lagrange test is used to compare the estimation by a pooled or POLS model and a random model. In Table 9 we present the results of this test which indicate that the best estimation is by random effects for the different models ($\text{chibar}_{(01)}^2 = 298.04$, p-value = 0.0000; $\text{chibar}_{(01)}^2 = 297.98$, p-value = 0.0000; $\text{chibar}_{(01)}^2 = 138.56$, p-value = 0.0000; $\text{chibar}_{(01)}^2 = 133.41$, p-value = 0.0000; respectively). For this reason, the Hausman test is performed to choose the random effects model over the fixed effects model. The results of the test statistic indicate that the random effects estimation is preferable because it produces a more efficient estimator than the fixed effects estimation model ($X_{(1)}^2 = 0.42$, p-value = 0.5175; $X_{(4)}^2 = 3.02$, p-value = 0.554; $X_{(1)}^2 = 1.37$, p-value = 0.2417; $X_{(4)}^2 = 6.69$, p-value = 0.1532; respectively).

The results show that, both in the estimation of the random effects model and the random effects model with robust errors for the interaction and information index, the population size has a positive and significant relationship in relation to the indexes ($\beta_1 = 6.34$, p-value = 0.00; $\beta_1 = 6.34$, p-value = 0.00; $\beta_1 = 6.22$, p-value = 0.00; $\beta_1 = 6.22$, p-value = 0.00, respectively).

If we consider the population by segments, we observe that the behavior is similar in both indexes. Thus, those municipalities with more than 5000 inhabitants have a significant and positive influence in relation to both indexes. The size of the municipality does not present a significant relationship with the participation index and the information index only in the case of municipalities with a population of less than 5000 inhabitants.

6. Discussion and conclusions

The aim of this paper was to provide empirical evidence on how local governments in Portugal use online media to improve municipal transparency, opening new space for political communication and participation, thus improving their interaction with society. The aim was to analyze the evolution in the use of these mechanisms of communication and citizen participation, as well as to contrast whether the size of the municipality is a factor that determines the level of disclosure and participation observed.

Our results show that municipalities are increasingly committed to develop online citizen participation initiatives, increasing transparency and participation mechanisms significantly over the years. However, there is still work to be done to improve the current level of transparency and participation in Portuguese municipalities. The calculated municipal information index presents average values in the period analyzed (70.77) significantly higher than the average values of the participation index (50). In both cases there is a favorable evolution of these indicators throughout the period analyzed. These results have allowed us to verify hypotheses H1 and H2 that were initially proposed.

Despite the potential opportunities offered by social media to build and strengthen relationships with society, the use of social media by Portuguese municipal governments is only in its initial phase. The level of development is fundamentally oriented towards transmitting information and less towards the implementation of citizen participation channels based on e-government. Thus, we can accept the third hypothesis. This is in line with the results found by Ramírez et al. [14] for the Spanish case and Bonsón et al. [24] for EU local governments. These

Table 9
Results of panel data regression using random effects.

Dependent variable	independent variable							
	Participation Index				Information Index			
	[1]	[2] ^a	[3]	[4] ^b	[5]	[6] ^c	[7]	[8] ^d
Population	6.34*** (1.02)	6.34*** (0.97)			6.22*** (0.99)	6.22*** (0.91)		
Segment population (inhabitants):								
<5000			1.43 (4.02)	1.43 (4.44)			6.22 (3.96)	6.22 (4.14)
≥5000; <10,000			9.99** (4.09)	9.99** (4.37)			14.91*** (4.02)	14.91*** (4.04)
≥10,000; <20,000			13.66*** (4.16)	13.66*** (4.33)			18.41*** (4.08)	18.41*** (4.19)
≥20,000; <50,000			19.80*** (4.22)	19.80*** (4.44)			21.72*** (4.13)	21.72*** (4.03)
(Constant)	-11.95 (9.99)	-11.95 (9.67)	40.48*** (3.36)	40.48*** (3.71)	10.01 (9.78)	10.01 (9.17)	57.52*** (3.29)	57.52*** (3.40)
Remarks	803	803	803	803	803	803	803	803
Wald χ^2	38.95***	42.68***	39.22***	39.49***	39.03***	47.02***	42.42***	42.07***
R ² overall	0.0979	0.0979	0.0982	0.0982	0.0821	0.0821	0.0912	0.0912
Rho	0.6102	0.6102	0.6133	0.6133	0.4232	0.4232	0.4204	0.4204
Breusch-Pagan Lagrange	chibar ₍₀₁₎ ² = 298.04*** (p-value = 0.000)		chibar ₍₀₁₎ ² = 297.98*** (p-value = 0.000)		chibar ₍₀₁₎ ² = 138.56*** (p-value = 0.000)		chibar ₍₀₁₎ ² = 133.41*** (p-value = 0.000)	
F test	F _(267, 534) = 5.68*** (p-value = 0.000)		F _(267, 531) = 5.68*** (p-value = 0.000)		F _(267, 534) = 3.188*** (p-value = 0.000)		F _(267, 531) = 3.14*** (p-value = 0.000)	
Hausman Test	$\chi^2_{(1)} = 0.42$ (p-value = 0.5175)		$\chi^2_{(4)} = 3.02$ (p-value = 0.554)		$\chi^2_{(1)} = 1.37$ (p-value = 0.2417)		$\chi^2_{(4)} = 6.69$ (p-value = 0.1532)	

Note: The numbers in parentheses represent the values of the standard errors. a, b, c and d are estimated models with robust errors. Asterisks represent the significance level of variables. *p < 0.1; **p < 0.05; ***p < 0.01.

Source: Own elaboration

studies point out that local governments are using Web 2.0 and social media tools to enhance transparency. However, in general, their use to promote e-participation is still in their infancy at the local level.

In relation to the first indicator, information index, the results obtained allow us to affirm that there is greater awareness and willingness of local governments to implement initiatives and mechanisms related to the provision of information to citizens and society. These results are in line with the findings found by other studies such as those of Cárcaba and García [66]; Guillamón et al. [85]; Serrano et al. [71]; Navarro et al. [86]; Cuadrado et al. Cuadrado et al. [12]; Bayona and Morales [7] and Tejedo-Romero and Araujo [16], among others.

This increase in online information available to citizens offers benefits to citizens and other stakeholders, including higher transparency and accountability [87,88], citizen empowerment, as well as more citizen involvement in government activities [89].

In terms of information transparency of municipal governments, we can highlight the existence of a search engine in almost all the websites of Portuguese municipalities, while the existence of information systems or the publication of the municipality’s operating hours is reduced to two thirds of the total, with greater presence as the municipality’s size increases. The publication of protocols and resolutions on subsidies and the use of movable property by associations, is only present in half of the municipalities that publish information online, and it increases with size of the municipality. Thus, we corroborate our fourth hypothesis.

This means that the need to transmit information to citizens, who are at the ones who vote for politicians, is aimed to maintain the trust placed in them, showing an adequate information transparency that they demand. The desire of governments to legitimize their existence in society, based on the theory of legitimacy, is what drives them to increase the information they make available to citizens.

In relation to the participation index, it allows us to corroborate Hypothesis 5 regarding the existence of significant differences in the implementation of online citizen participation initiatives depending on the population size of the municipality. In addition, it is verified that this phase of e-government presents a significant delay with respect to the implementation of online mechanisms of information transparency.

With respect to initiatives and mechanisms related to interaction with citizens and society, only the existence of links to active social networks stands out positively. These are available in 90% of the municipalities. The larger the municipalities, the greater the number of initiatives. The existence of channels for complaints and suggestions is present in two thirds of the municipalities. The difference is especially significant among the larger municipalities, where the channel exists in 77% of the municipalities, compared to 50% of the smaller ones. The existence of an information service for online administrative procedures is only limited to 62.7% of the larger municipalities. The percentage of municipalities offering this service drops significantly as the size of the municipality decreases. The ombudsman with publication of the statute and contact is practically non-existent in most of the municipalities, reaching an average value of 5% of the municipalities analyzed.

It is found that the process of citizen participation through electronic media is a phase with less development, which is consistent with Sandoval-Almazán and Gil-García [31] and Panagiotopoulos et al. [90] who state that the interactions between citizens and governments remain at a rather informative level.

In addition, it was found that the size of the municipalities has a positive and significant influence on the development of initiatives and mechanisms related both to the information available to citizens and society and to their interaction with Portuguese municipalities. These results are in line with studies carried out to measure the transparency of local governments such as those of Cárcaba and García [66]; Albalade [74]; Alcaraz et al. [11]; Serrano et al. (2016); Guillamón et al. [75]; Gaia and Jones [91]; Navarro et al. [76]; Serrano et al. [71]; Ramírez et al. [14]. These studies show that population size has an impact on the use of social media in Spanish and Italian local governments for transparency purposes. Similarly, Pina et al. [15] also identified population size as a variable to understand the level of development of municipal websites in the European Union.

The influence of population size corroborated in this research occurs for both information dissemination and the establishment of citizen participation mechanisms. This finding is aligned with studies that find that size is an important environmental factor contributing to encourage

municipalities to develop their e-government arrangements [44,92,40], increase e-information provision [44,80], enhance e-services [45,79,80], and enhance e-participation [75,80,82]. Government plays the role of service and information provider and must meet the expectations of a densely populated area with many people by being more innovative [93].

In conclusion, information and participation indexes are significantly and positively influenced by the size of the municipality. It can be justified because larger municipalities face stronger and more varied demands for public services from different interest groups. They also are more politically visible to society. This encourages local governments to disseminate information and implement mechanisms for online citizen participation. This result is consistent with stakeholder theory and political cost theory, which confirm that larger local governments disclose more information to satisfy the information needs of a greater number and variety of stakeholders, who demand high transparency, and to mitigate external pressure and political costs. This evolution is in line with the findings of González Bustamante et al. [29] and Altman and Luna [94]; who state that e-government tends to minimize citizens' information costs, allowing the emergence of new vertical and horizontal accountability mechanisms.

Also, in larger municipalities, local governments use more social media applications to disclose information and reduce agency costs. Since these municipalities have greater information asymmetry problems, they may use more social media applications to promote immediate communication between politicians and citizens and reduce agency costs. Finally, this finding indicates that more effort should be devoted to improving online citizen information and participation systems in smaller municipalities.

The differences found among the different Portuguese municipalities lead us to conclude, following the approaches of Garcia (2013), that it seems necessary to establish national policies, laws or recommendations that generate similar levels of transparency among local governments to avoid social dilemmas.

In short, our findings for Portuguese local governments are in line with the international evolution that e-government models are experiencing at the municipal level [16,24,35,38]. E-government shows significant progress in terms of citizen satisfaction, reduction of bureaucratic attitudes in public institutions and significant resource savings. E-government is more than just a website, as it has added new concepts such as transparency, accountability and citizen participation in the evaluation of government performance.

6.1. Theoretical and practical implications

From a theoretical perspective, the paper has made significant contributions. It contributes to the scientific literature on the development of e-government by adding to the research that examines the development and current stages of e-government. This research analyzes e-government and e-governance in Portugal and provides evidence of the current stage of digital governance based on 268 municipalities analyzed in each of the years that made up the study period. It provides findings on the existing situation in the implementation of municipal e-government in Portugal according to the size of the municipality. This typology provides a basis for comparing the stages and determinants of e-government in different countries [13,14,38,40,72].

The results of the content analysis and regression analysis corroborate for Portugal the previous findings on the different institutional backgrounds associated with the different dimensions or areas of e-government practice. Likewise, they generate stronger research insights by systematically drawing on the information science literature, in addition to public administration and management. Since the results of this research suggest that municipality size is a determinant of the level of e-governance, future research could also address what other determinants influence e-governance and what the interdependence of these causal relationships might be. As the dimensions are not

independent of each other, there must be interactions between predictors and e-governance outcomes. Case-based approaches are appropriate for these types of questions, but so are quantitative approaches that focus on the relationships between a limited number of moderators and outcome variables. There may be more specific associations or combinations of factors associated with particular dimensions.

From a practical perspective, this paper offers a snapshot of how the dimension of the municipalities affects, over time, the implementation and development of e-government initiatives related to participatory processes and the channels to improve citizens' participation and interaction with society. The findings in this study provide to policy makers, regulators and public managers some important insights in relation to online transparency improvement by addressing issues related to both information and citizen participation mechanisms. In this sense, as a positive initiative, our results could be of interest to government authorities in order to identify that the size of the municipality significantly conditions the implementation of transparency mechanisms and e-government. In addition, it highlights which aspects should be advocated to improve e-government at the municipal management level. Policy makers within the local governments need to pay attention to the capabilities of e-governments tools to better facilitate the e-participation process and provide the necessary channels to get citizens' feedback.

Concerning decision makers at national level, this research alerts the need to increase resources allocation to small municipalities in order to invest on e-government to improve communication and citizen participation. Indeed, easy access to information through online disclosure of public information may improve citizens' ability to judge the administrative capacity of local governments and decide accordingly. All this will allow better monitoring of public activity and contribute to the necessary democratic regeneration, promote efficiency and effectiveness and favor economic growth.

These implications can be extended to the international context. Previous studies have concluded that the use of Web 2.0 and social media tools to promote e-participation are still in their infancy at the local. Therefore, our recommendations will be useful to managers, regulators, professional organizations, and policymakers of municipality in different countries.

Author statement

Francisca Tejedo-Romero: Conception and design of study, revising theoretical framework, acquisition of data, analysis and interpretation of data, Drafting the manuscript, revising the manuscript critically for important intellectual content, Approval of the version of the manuscript to be submitted. **Joaquim Filipe Ferraz Esteves Araujo:** Conception and design of study, revising theoretical framework, acquisition of data, analysis and interpretation of data, Drafting the manuscript, revising the manuscript critically for important intellectual content, Approval of the version of the manuscript to be submitted. **Ángel Tejada:** Writing theoretical draft; interpretation of data, Drafting the manuscript, revising the manuscript critically for important intellectual content, Approval of the version of the manuscript to be submitted. **Yolanda Ramírez:** Revising the manuscript critically for important intellectual content, Approval of the version of the manuscript to be submitted.

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